

أرجوزة الولدان (Urjuzat al-Wildan)

also known as "Islamic Jureisprudence", "منظومة القرطبي"

By Bilyaminu Muhammad, Umaru Musa 'Yar-Adua University Katsina, Nigeria

Entry tags: Islamic Traditions, Religious Group, Text, Fiqh

The text was prepared by Imam Yahya al-Qurtabi, on the Islamic Jurisprudence to highlight religious principles of the Islamic creed system (Tauheed), Worship (Ibadat), and some areas of the social interaction (Mu'amalat) based on the analyzed guidelines of the Maliki School of Law, which remained the most widely adopted school of Law in the western region of the Muslim populace environment. The text was composed in stanzas for easy memorization to most people, especially children who chanted the poem during their leisure time to enable them to understand Islamic Law most easily.

Date Range: 1403 CE - 1445 CE

Region: Sokoto

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Benin, Burkina Faso, Niger, Togo, Nigeria, Chad, Cameroon

Sokoto around 1870, during the reign of Ahmadu Rufai. Adapted from AbdurRahman AbdulMoneim [https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_\(cropped\).pr](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_(cropped).pr)

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: قرطبي، ي. (1235). أرجوزة الولدان. كاتو، نيجيرية

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP1101-1-27#?xywh=-3015%2C-777%2C10028%2C6666&c=0&m=0&s=0&cv=0>

– Source 1 Description: الفقه الإسلامي, British Library, EAP1101/1/27, <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP1101-1-27>

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.noor-book.com/%D9%83%D8%AA%D8%A7%D8%A8-%D9%85%D9%86%D8%B8%D9%88%D9%85%D9%87-%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%82%D8%B1%D8%B7%D8%A8%D9%8A-%D9%86-pdf>

– Source 1 Description: Noor Book website

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb

– No

Notes: The text was not stored in any tomb.

↳ Cemetery

– No

Notes: The text was not kept in any cemetery, as Islam prohibits that.

↳ Temple

– No

Notes: The text was not kept in any temple, as Islam did not pay any importance to it.

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

Notes: The text is not kept on altar.

↳ Devotional marker

– No

Notes: The text is not stored at the devotional marker.

↳ Cenotaph

– No

Notes: The text is not kept in the cenotaph.

↳ Church

– No

Notes: The text is not stored in the church, as Islam has no business with it.

↳ Mosque

– Yes

Notes: Some copies are stored in mosques for the benefit of Muslims.

↳ Synagogue

– No

Notes: The text is not stored at the synagogue.

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

Notes: The text is not stored at the triumphal arch.

↳ Monument

– No

Notes: The text is not kept in the monument.

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

Notes: The text is kept at mass gathering points apart from schools and mosques.

↳ Cave(s)

– No

Notes: The text is not kept in a cave.

↳ Hilltops

– No

Notes: The text is not stored on hilltops.

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

Notes: The text is not kept in other natural sanctuaries.

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

Notes: The text is not stored at boundary markers.

↳ Domestic contexts

– Yes

Notes: Many copies are kept in a domestic context for personal use.

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: Many copies are kept in libraries and archives for the benefit of students and other researchers.

↳ Specify

– Specify: Book shops

Methods of Composition

– Written

Notes: The text was a handwritten copy of the book.

↳ Inked

– with Ink

Notes: The text was written with black ink, as observed in the attached paper.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Notes: The text was written on brown-colored paper, as observed in the attached sample.

↳ Specify type of paper

– Specify: Brown colour

Notes: The attached sample identified the color of the paper.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Notes: There is no image or iconography accompanied by where the text is kept.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Notes: The paper was prepared physically to support a copy of the text.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no iconic image in the area where the text is kept.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Notes: The text was not modified before a copy of the text.

Materiality

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Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: Prize was given to the author on account of his work

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

Notes: The polity established a paper production factory to support its production and other religious books in general

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– Yes

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

Notes: Some political officials assisted in the production of the text

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

Notes: Political official and religious officials support each other

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– Yes

Notes: The polity enforced religious observance in accordance with the prescription of the text

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– Yes

Notes: The legal code of the polity is in agreement with the content of the text

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

↳ Present full-time?

– Yes

↳ Present part-time?

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– No

Notes: No gender segregation

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– No

Notes: They engaged in other activities

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– No

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– No

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

Notes: Schools are established for training other specialists

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– Yes

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Total audience: 200000000

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

– Number: 1000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 100000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 2000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Conversion to the religion of Islam

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

– Number: 10000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 8000000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 100000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Conversion to the religion and migration

↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

– No

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated by the text for all adherents?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing or missionary work part of the historical culture of the community referenced in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

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– Yes

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– Yes

- ↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for religious professionals?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for all adherents?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for religious professionals?
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- ↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?
 - No
- ↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?
 - No
 - ↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?
 - No
 - ↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?
 - No
- ↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?
 - No

Notes: Non-muslims

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: The book was only prepared on the prescription of the Qur'an

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

Notes: The text was written in the Arabic language

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– No

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Prophet

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– Yes

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– Yes

Notes: The text is being interpreted in other languages to advance the study of the text

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Stanzas of the text are being chanted orally to support the study of the text

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Notes: The text can not be recited in prayers

Is there material significance to the text?

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Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned the name of the angel Jibril as part of the spirit body.

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Notes: The spirit mind is conceived to have the power of paster movement beyond the capability of humans.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

Notes: Spirit body is not visible and untouchable.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

Notes: The mentioned spirit is made to convey divine messages to prophets.

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– No

Notes: No distinction.

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

Notes: The practitioners did not engage debate on mind body dualism.

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention any debate.

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Notes: The corporal body is to perish after death, while the soul is to remain forever.

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

Notes: The text did not further any debate.

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– I don't know

Notes: The text did not make a distinction on the opinion of any group.

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: God is ever monitoring the activities of humans.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

Notes: The text stated supernatural on prosocial norms.

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

Notes: The ritual offering does not attract supernatural monitoring.

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– No

Notes: Supernatural being prohibits taboos.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

Notes: They do not like the killing of coreligionists.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Yes

Notes: They observed it prohibited except in due cause.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Field doesn't know

Notes: They record it as part of the prohibited act.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

Notes: They do not have a desire for sex.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

Notes: They considered it prohibited and hence recorded it as a sin.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings record honoring oaths as a good act.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings care about laziness and record it as sin act.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
 - Yes
 - Notes: They hate it for the prohibition of God on it.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - Yes
 - Notes: They considered it a wrong act.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural beings hate shirking risk.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - I don't know
 - Notes: Supernatural beings hate disrespect to elders.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - Yes
 - Notes: They considered it prohibited.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - Yes
 - Notes: They record it as a sin against the doer.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
 - Notes: They usually attend places of ritual duties, such as prayers.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural beings were assigned (by God) to record those observing them properly.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural beings care about economic fairness.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings do not approach those who are impure.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings do not need a place.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: Supernatural beings care about other creatures, especially humans and jinns.

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Notes: The text is a manual for some Islamic practices, such as prayer, fasting, etc.

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The text does not require celibacy.

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: The text restricted discussion on Worship (Ibadat) alone.

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text identified Imam Mahadi who is to come towards the end of the world.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: The time of his coming is not known.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

Notes: His purpose is to save humanity.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– Yes

Notes: He is to restore just rule on earth.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– Yes

Notes: Mahadi is to restore the religious tradition of Islam.

↳ Other purpose

– Specify: He is to save people from the delusion of the devil and Dajjal (deceiver).

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Notes: The text is not accompanied by art.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: The text accepted lineages established on Islamic principles and guidelines.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text stated belief in the afterlife.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: The text did not specify a place for the afterlife.

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: The religious group believed in the undoubtful occurrence of the afterlife.

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Notes: The religious group believed that Arabic would be the language of the afterlife.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The text did not restricted sexual activity, except out of wedlock, which is considered prohibited.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The whole discussion was made on religious worship (Ibadat) alone.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Escatology was presented in the text.

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

Notes: It will happen in the afterlife.

↳ At specified time in future

– No

Notes: The time is not known to anybody.

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– No

Notes: Its time is not known.

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

Notes: The exact time is not known.

↳ At some other time [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The time is only known by God.

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

Notes: Adherents cannot bring the end of this world.

↳ Divine judgment event

– Yes

Notes: Divine judgment is to be in the afterlife.

↳ Restoration of the world

– No

Notes: The present world is to be substituted by another.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– Yes

Notes: Temporal life is to happen in the grave.

↳ Establishment of new political system

– No

Notes: There will not be a new political system.

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

Notes: Religion is to end in this world.

↳ Other form of eschatology?

– Specify: Paradise and Hellfire.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– No

Notes: None will survive the eschaton except God alone.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: The punishment is only in the hereafter.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: There were published and handwritten versions of the text.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: Both versions are considered proper.

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– No

Notes: There is no difference in the versions, except little error that might happen in the act of copying or typing.

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: There is no debate on the versions since both are considered proper.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Notes: The text does not require castration.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

Notes: The text analyzed legal codes applicable to Muslims.

Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned some formal institutions; attached to the polity, such as the police guard, judicial system, etc.

Is there an institutionalized police force whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– I don't know

Notes: The text stated principles to all in addition to the police force of the state.

Is there an institutionalized judicial system whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

Notes: Activities of the judicial system are expected to go along with the prescription of the text.

Does the text in question specify institutionalized punishment?

– Yes

Notes: The text institutionalized punishment of those who violated the principles of Islamic Law.

Execution?

– Yes

Notes: Those to have made apostasy from Islam are judged to execution.

Exile?

– Yes

Notes: Those to have rebel the Islamic state are judged to exile.

Corporal punishments?

– Yes

Notes: The text identified those to have committed fornication or drink alcohol

are to receive corporal punishment.

↳ Ostracism?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention any punishment for ostracism.

↳ Seizure of property?

– Yes

Notes: Obligatory charity (Zakat) shall be collected by force from the defaulters.

↳ Are there any established institutionalized rewards specified in the text?

– Yes

Notes: There are some rewards for praised-worthy activities.

↳ Grants of property?

– Yes

Notes: The reward is only promised in the hereafter.

↳ Social promotion?

– Yes

Notes: Rewards are promised to those brought what could benefit Muslims and Islam.

↳ Financial rewards?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: A reward is promised in the hereafter.

↳ Implied financial rewards (tax exemption)?

– No

Notes: No tax exemption.

↳ Grants of labor?

– No

Notes: The reward is only expected from Allah.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Notes: Reincarnation is not accepted in the religion of the text.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: The text is not part of the other collection of texts.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: They only record good deeds for God to reward its doer.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Notes: The text is restricted to a system of worship alone, without pointing to Islamic ethics (Akhlaq).

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: The text made a chapter on fasting.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Notes: Corpses of the adherents shall be buried after death.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: The text is part of the literary tradition of the Islamic Jurisprudence.

Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: The text identified the manner of performing some daily religious activities, especially prayer, Zakat, etc.

Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: The text prescribed acceptable traits and behaviors in Islam.

Other

–Other [specify]: The text served as guideline on some daily interaction of the people.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

Notes: The text goes along with the Islamic lunar calendar when performing some religious duties, such

as fasting during the month of Ramadan.

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Lunar?

Notes: The text was designed on the lunar hijrah calendar.

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

Notes: The text identified specified periods of performing some religious duties.

↳ Planting?

– No

Notes: Planting is only done when rain falls.

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– No

Notes: The text did not state that.

↳ Harvest?

– No

Notes: Harvest is only done when the crop is ripe.

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– Yes

Notes: A naming ceremony is done on the seventh day of the child's birth.

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– Yes

Notes: The first haircut is done on the seventh day of childbirth.

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– No

Notes: No ceremony is done for puberty attainment or adulthood.

↳ Marriage?

– Yes

Notes: Marriage is done when the spouse got mature.

- ↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?
 - No
 - Notes: No specified time is attached to the establishment of a home.

- ↳ Divorce?
 - No
 - Notes: No period is identified for the pronouncement of divorce.

- ↳ Warfare?
 - No
 - Notes: No period is identified for warfare.

- ↳ Funerary services?
 - No
 - Notes: No period is restricted to funerary services in the text.

- ↳ Trade/commerce?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Trade/commerce is only restricted in the time of prayer.

- ↳ Festivals?
 - I don't know
 - Notes: The Festival is done annually during the Eid al-Fitr and Eid al-Adha periods.

- ↳ Pilgrimages?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Pilgrimage is stipulated to the month of zul-Qi'adah and zul-Hajj.

- ↳ How strict are the stipulations regarding pilgrimage?
 - obligatory for all
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Notes: The identified pilgrimage is only done in Arabia.

↳ Is the pilgrimage conducted by walking or by other means?

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Notes: Feasting is done in some ceremonial instances of marriage.

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed in accordance with the guidelines of the text?

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Notes: The text recommends the slaughter of a ram at the event of a feast for people to eat.

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that produced the text/copies of the text?

– No

Notes: Feasting is done on individual capabilities.

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific locations in accordance with guidelines from the text?

– No

Notes: Feasting is recommended to be done at the place of the wedding ceremony.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Notes: The text prohibits co-sacrifice in the burial of the adherents.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: The text advocated for Lawful food.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Notes: The text did not allow permanent scarring of the body.

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Notes: It only directed the corpses to be buried alone.

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Burial is to be done immediately after the death of the adherent.

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

Notes: Cenotaphs are not allowed in Islam.

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

Notes: The burial is always done in the cemetery.

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

Notes: The family tomb is not mentioned in the text.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

Notes: The text encouraged burial in the cemetery alone, except for miscarriage which could be buried at home.

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

Notes: A Normal burial is only approved by the text.

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

–Specify: Funeral prayer

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Notes: The text does not direct inflict a wound on any part of a body.

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Notes: The text does not require the sacrifice of an adult.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Notes: Only bathing and shrowding are associated with funerary practices.

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned a supernatural being that has control over all creations.

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned the supreme high God.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

Notes: The text did not describe the supreme high God in anthropomorphic terms.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Notes: The text identified the supreme high God as the sky deity.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

Notes: The text did not describe the supreme high God as chthonic.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

Notes: Supreme high God is described as one alone.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

Notes: The monarch is nothing but a servant of the high God.

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites
 - No
 - Notes: Elits have no kin relation to the high God.

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
 - No
 - Notes: High God does not have a loyalty relation to the elites.

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
 - Yes
 - Notes: High God is unquestionable in all His activities.

- ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
 - Specify: Power to control other creatures.

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - Notes: High God is aware of everything in the world.

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - Notes: His knowledge extends to all affairs of humans.

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - Notes: Knowledge of the High God has no restriction.

- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
 - Notes: His knowledge is beyond restriction.

- ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
 - Yes
 - Notes: His knowledge is unrestricted outside the sample region.

- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - Notes: High God can see everywhere.

- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - Notes: High God can see everywhere.

- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
 - Notes: High God has the power to see inside the mind.

- ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
 - Notes: High God knows the basic character of humans.

- ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes
 - Notes: His power determine what human shall do in his life.

- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - Notes: High God knows everything in this world.

- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
 - Notes: He has the power to cause everything in this world.

- ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
 - Notes: He rewards on good deeds of humans and jinns.

- ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
 - Notes: He is to punish wrongdoers in the hereafter.

- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
 - Notes: His power cause efficacy of the world.

- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes

Notes: His emotion could not be comprehended.

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– Yes

Notes: His emotion could not be understood.

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

Notes: He does not have a need for food.

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

Notes: High God cannot be hurt.

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

Notes: High God cannot be tricked.

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– I don't know

Notes: High God cannot be imprisoned.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

Notes: None should be worshiped except Him alone.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: The existence of creatures exhibits His presence.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Notes: High God communicates with messengers and prophets alone.

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

Notes: High God communicates to some messengers in awake time, such as prophet Moses (A.S).

↳ In dreams

– Yes

Notes: He communicates to the prophet Abraham through dreams.

↳ In trance possession

– Yes

Notes: If He so wishes.

↳ Through divination practices

– No

Notes: He communicates even without divine practices.

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

Notes: He communicates through religious specialists.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: He does not communicate with the monarch.

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: Communication could be made through Angels.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Notes: Communication with the high God is not possible through the text.

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Notes: The text prohibited the sacrifice of children.

Previously human spirits are present

– I don't know

Notes: The text mentioned the human spirit.

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Notes: The text prohibited suicide.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: Angels are described as non-human spirits.

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings can only be seen by prophets or those at the sport of dying.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings can not physically be felt.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Nonhuman spirit knows this world.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge of the nonhuman spirit could not extend to what is in the mind.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge of the nonhuman spirit is restricted to the physical affairs of humans.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge is not restricted to the sampled region.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge is unrestricted outside the sample region.

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Notes: They can observe humans in public.

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Notes: They can see humans everywhere.

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– No

Notes: They can see hidden motives in the mind.

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Notes: They comprehend personal essence.

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– I don't know

Notes: They cannot foresight the future.

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: They may know about other creatures apart from humans.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings cannot cause efficacy of the world.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings may communicate to prophets on the directives of Allah.

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

Notes: But to prophets.

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

Notes: They may appear in dreams.

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

Notes: They may appear in a trance.

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

Notes: Islam did not approve divine practices that might cause the appearance of supernatural beings.

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: common people.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings do not have indirect efficacy causal in the world.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

Notes: Their emotions could not be comprehended.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

Notes: They do not exhibit negative emotions.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

Notes: They do not possess hunger.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: Not known.

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Notes: The text encouraged voluntary charity (Sadaqah) and Zakat.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text intensified the attendance of the congregational daily prayers at mosques.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: The text did not attest to pantheon supernatural beings.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention mixed human-divine beings.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– I don't know

Notes: The text does not require approaching any dangerous act.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Notes: The text does not attract the presence of supernatural beings.

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: The text encouraged accepting ethical precepts.

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: Jinns are present.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text encouraged kindness to all.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: The text does not guide divination practice.

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires participation in religious services.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 2

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed for the attendance of Hajj that unit people from all parts of the world.

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Number of participants: 2000000

Notes: Annual hajj could gather about the high population of people from various sections of the world.

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Hours: 8760

Notes: Hours of the year in which the hajj occasion takes place.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

Notes: A chapter was made in the text on the Annual Hajj occasion.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– No

Notes: The service does not entail synchronic practices.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Notes: All intoxicants are prohibited.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text advocated for some group markers activities.

↳ Tattoos/scarification?

– No

Notes: Tattoos are not mentioned in the text.

↳ Circumcision?

– Yes

Notes: The text recommended circumcision in male children.

↳ Food taboos?

– No

↳ Hair?

– Yes

Notes: The text recommended hair cut.

↳ Dress?

– Yes

Notes: The text recommended dressing neat to all.

↳ Ornaments?

– Yes

Notes: Gold ornaments are only meant to women alone.

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: Naming ceremony.

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Notes: The text did not employ kinship terminology.

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Notes: The text restricted discussion on worship (Ibadat).

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

Notes: The text recommended the sacrifice of Animals.

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Notes: Sacrifice at the event of eid and Hajj.

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

Notes: Humans are not subject to sacrifice.

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

Notes: Self-sacrifice is not present in the text.

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned obligatory charity.

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Yes

Notes: Zakat is obligatory for those having the amount.

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

Notes: The objects are crops, ornaments and articles of trade.

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Yes

Notes: Food crops are part of them.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– No

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– No

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings?
(I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: The text mentioned Sadaqah

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Yes

Notes: Attendance to congregational prayer is obligatory.

↳ By the community?

– Yes

Notes: The worship was made at a mosque.

↳ By specific individuals?

– No

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention the principle of the places of worship.

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Notes: The text is not accompanied by art.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: There were published and handwritten versions of the text.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: Both versions are considered proper.

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– No

Notes: There is no difference in the versions, except little error that might happen in the act of copying or typing.

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: There is no debate on the versions since both are considered proper.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: The text is not part of the other collection of texts.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: The text is part of the literary tradition of the Islamic Jurisprudence.

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: The text identified the manner of performing some daily religious activities, especially prayer, Zakat, etc.

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: The text prescribed acceptable traits and behaviors in Islam.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: The text served as guideline on some daily interaction of the people.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Notes: The text is a manual for some Islamic practices, such as prayer, fasting, etc.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: The text accepted lineages established on Islamic principles and guidelines.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

Notes: The text analyzed legal codes applicable to Muslims.

↳ Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned some formal institutions; attached to the polity, such as the police guard, judicial system, etc.

↳ Is there an institutionalized police force whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

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Notes: The text stated principles to all in addition to the police force of the state.

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– Yes

Notes: Activities of the judicial system are expected to go along with the prescription of the text.

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Notes: The text institutionalized punishment of those who violated the principles of Islamic Law.

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– Yes

Notes: Those to have made apostasy from Islam are judged to execution.

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Notes: Those to have rebel the Islamic state are judged to exile.

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Notes: The reward is only promised in the hereafter.

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Notes: Rewards are promised to those brought what could benefit Muslims and Islam.

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Notes: Marriage is done when the spouse got mature.

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Notes: No specified time is attached to the establishment of a home.

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Notes: Feasting is recommended to be done at the place of the wedding ceremony.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned the name of the angel Jibril as part of the spirit body.

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Notes: The spirit mind is conceived to have the power of paster movement beyond the capability of humans.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

Notes: Spirit body is not visible and untouchable.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

Notes: The mentioned spirit is made to convey divine messages to prophets.

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– No

Notes: No distinction.

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

Notes: The practitioners did not engage in debate on mind-body dualism.

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention any debate.

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Notes: The corporeal body is to perish after death, while the soul is to remain forever.

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

Notes: The text did not further any debate.

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– I don't know

Notes: The text did not make a distinction on the opinion of any group.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text stated belief in the afterlife.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: The text did not specify a place for the afterlife.

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: The religious group believed in the undoubtful occurrence of the afterlife.

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Notes: The religious group believed that Arabic would be the language of the afterlife.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Notes: Reincarnation is not accepted in the religion of the text.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Notes: Corpses of the adherents shall be buried after death.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Notes: The text prohibits co-sacrifice in the burial of the adherents.

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Notes: It only directed the corpses to be buried alone.

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Burial is to be done immediately after the death of the adherent.

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

Notes: Cenotaphs are not allowed in Islam.

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

Notes: The burial is always done in the cemetery.

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

Notes: The family tomb is not mentioned in the text.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

Notes: The text encouraged burial in the cemetery alone, except for miscarriage which could be buried at home.

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

Notes: A Normal burial is only approved by the text.

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: Funeral prayer

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Notes: Only bathing and shrowding are associated with funerary practices.

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned a supernatural being that has control over all creations.

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned the supreme high God.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

Notes: The text did not describe the supreme high God in anthropomorphic terms.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Notes: The text identified the supreme high God as the sky deity.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

Notes: The text did not describe the supreme high God as chthonic.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

Notes: Supreme high God is described as one alone.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

Notes: The monarch is nothing but a servant of the high God.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

Notes: Elites have no kin relation to the high God.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

Notes: High God does not have a loyalty relation to the elites.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

Notes: High God is unquestionable in all His activities.

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: Power to control other creatures.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: High God is aware of everything in the world.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Notes: His knowledge extends to all affairs of humans.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Notes: Knowledge of the High God has no restriction.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Notes: His knowledge is beyond restriction.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
– Yes
Notes: His knowledge is unrestricted outside the sample region.

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– Yes
Notes: High God can see everywhere.

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– Yes
Notes: High God can see everywhere.

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– Yes
Notes: High God has the power to see inside the mind.

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
– Yes
Notes: High God knows the basic character of humans.

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– Yes
Notes: His power determine what human shall do in his life.

↳ Has other knowledge of this world
– Yes
Notes: High God knows everything in this world.

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes
Notes: He has the power to cause everything in this world.

↳ Can reward
– Yes
Notes: He rewards on good deeds of humans and jinns.

↳ Can punish
– Yes

Notes: He is to punish wrongdoers in the hereafter.

- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
 - Notes: His power cause efficacy of the world.
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes
 - Notes: His emotion could not be comprehended.
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - Yes
 - Notes: His emotion could not be understood.
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No
 - Notes: He does not have a need for food.
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
 - Notes: High God cannot be hurt.
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
 - Notes: High God cannot be tricked.
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - I don't know
 - Notes: High God cannot be imprisoned.
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - No
 - Notes: None should be worshiped except Him alone.
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
 - Specify: The existence of creatures exhibits His presence.
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Notes: High God communicates with messengers and prophets alone.

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

Notes: High God communicates to some messengers in awake time, such as prophet Moses (A.S).

↳ In dreams

– Yes

Notes: He communicates to the prophet Abraham through dreams.

↳ In trance possession

– Yes

Notes: If He so wishes.

↳ Through divination practices

– No

Notes: He communicates even without divine practices.

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

Notes: He communicates through religious specialists.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: He does not communicate with the monarch.

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: Communication could be made through Angels.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Notes: Communication with the high God is not possible through the text.

Previously human spirits are present

– I don't know

Notes: The text mentioned the human spirit.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: Angels are described as non-human spirits.

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings can only be seen by prophets or those at the sport of dying.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings can not physically be felt.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Nonhuman spirit knows this world.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge of the nonhuman spirit could not extend to what is in the mind.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge of the nonhuman spirit is restricted to the physical affairs of humans.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge is not restricted to the sampled region.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge is unrestricted outside the sample region.

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Notes: They can observe humans in public.

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Notes: They can see humans everywhere.

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– No

Notes: They can see hidden motives in the mind.

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Notes: They comprehend personal essence.

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– I don't know

Notes: They cannot foresight the future.

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: They may know about other creatures apart from humans.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings cannot cause efficacy of the world.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings may communicate to prophets on the directives of Allah.

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

Notes: But to prophets.

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

Notes: They may appear in dreams.

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

Notes: They may appear in a trance.

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

Notes: Islam did not approve divine practices that might cause the appearance of supernatural beings.

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: common people.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings do not have indirect efficacy causal in the world.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

Notes: Their emotions could not be comprehended.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

Notes: They do not exhibit negative emotions.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

Notes: They do not possess hunger.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

–Specify: Not known.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: The text did not attest to pantheon supernatural beings.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention mixed human-divine beings.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Notes: The text does not attract the presence of supernatural beings.

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Jinns are present.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: The text does not guide divination practice.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: God is ever monitoring the activities of humans.

There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

Notes: The text stated supernatural on prosocial norms.

Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

Notes: The ritual offering does not attract supernatural monitoring.

Supernatural being care about taboos

– No

Notes: Supernatural being prohibits taboos.

Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

Notes: They do not like the killing of coreligionists.

Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Yes

Notes: They observed it prohibited except in due cause.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Field doesn't know

Notes: They record it as part of the prohibited act.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

Notes: They do not have a desire for sex.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

Notes: They considered it prohibited and hence recorded it as a sin.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings record honoring oaths as a good act.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings care about laziness and record it as sin act.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

Notes: They hate it for the prohibition of God on it.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– Yes

Notes: They considered it a wrong act.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings hate shirking risk.

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– I don't know

Notes: Supernatural beings hate disrespect to elders.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - Yes
 - Notes: They considered it prohibited.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - Yes
 - Notes: They record it as a sin against the doer.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
 - Notes: They usually attend places of ritual duties, such as prayers.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural beings were assigned (by God) to record those observing them properly.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural beings care about economic fairness.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural beings do not approach those who are impure.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
 - No
 - Notes: Supernatural beings do not need a place.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other
 - Specify: Supernatural beings care about other creatures, especially humans and jinns.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: The punishment is only in the hereafter.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: They only record good deeds for God to reward its doer.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text identified Imam Mahadi who is to come towards the end of the world.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: The time of his coming is not known.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

Notes: His purpose is to save humanity.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– Yes

Notes: He is to restore just rule on earth.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– Yes

Notes: Mahadi is to restore the religious tradition of Islam.

↳ Other purpose

–Specify: He is to save people from the delusion of the devil and Dajjal (deceiver).

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Eschatology was presented in the text.

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

Notes: It will happen in the afterlife.

↳ At specified time in future

– No

Notes: The time is not known to anybody.

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– No

Notes: Its time is not known.

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

Notes: The exact time is not known.

↳ At some other time [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The time is only known by God.

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

Notes: Adherents cannot bring the end of this world.

↳ Divine judgment event

– Yes

Notes: Diven judgment is to be in the afterlife.

↳ Restoration of the world

– No

Notes: The present world is to be substituted by another.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– Yes

Notes: Temporal life is to happen in the grave.

↳ Establishment of new political system

– No

Notes: There will not be a new political system.

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

Notes: Religion is to end in this world.

↳ Other form of eschatology?

– Specify: Paradise and Hellfire.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– No

Notes: None will survive the eschaton except God alone.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: The text restricted discussion on Worship (Ibadat) alone.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The whole discussion was made on religious worship (Ibadat) alone.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Notes: The text is restricted to a system of worship alone, without pointing to Islamic ethics (Akhlaq).

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The text does not require celibacy.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The text did not restricted sexual activity, except out of wedlock, which is considered prohibited.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Notes: The text does not require castration.

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: The text made a chapter on fasting.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: The text advocated for Lawful food.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Notes: The text did not allow permanent scarring of the body.

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Notes: The text does not direct inflict a wound on any part of a body.

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Notes: The text does not require the sacrifice of an adult.

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Notes: The text prohibited the sacrifice of children.

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Notes: The text prohibited suicide.

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Notes: The text encouraged voluntary charity (Sadaqah) and Zakat.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text intensified the attendance of the congregational daily prayers at mosques.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– I don't know

Notes: The text does not require approaching any dangerous act.

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: The text encouraged accepting ethical precepts.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text encouraged kindness to all.

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires participation in religious services.

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 2

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed for the attendance of Hajj that unit people from all parts of the world.

On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Number of participants: 2000000

Notes: Annual hajj could gather about the high population of people from various sections of the world.

Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Hours: 8760

Notes: Hours of the year in which the hajj occasion takes place.

Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

Notes: A chapter was made in the text on the Annual Hajj occasion.

Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– No

Notes: The service does not entail synchronic practices.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Notes: All intoxicants are prohibited.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text advocated for some group markers activities.

↳ Tattoos/scarification?

– No

Notes: Tattoos are not mentioned in the text.

↳ Circumcision?

– Yes

Notes: The text recommended circumcision in male children.

↳ Food taboos?

– No

↳ Hair?

– Yes

Notes: The text recommended hair cut.

↳ Dress?

– Yes

Notes: The text recommended dressing neat to all.

↳ Ornaments?

– Yes

Notes: Gold ornaments are only meant to women alone.

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: Naming ceremony.

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Notes: The text did not employ kinship terminology.

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Notes: The text restricted discussion on worship (Ibadat).

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

Notes: The text recommended the sacrifice of Animals.

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Notes: Sacrifice at the event of eid and Hajj.

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

Notes: Humans are not subject to sacrifice.

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

Notes: Self-sacrifice is not present in the text.

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned obligatory charity.

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Yes

Notes: Zakat is obligatory for those having the amount.

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

Notes: The objects are crofs, ornaments and articles of trade.

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Yes

Notes: Food crops are part of them.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– No

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– No

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: The text mentioned Sadaqah

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Yes

Notes: Attendance to congregational prayer is obligatory.

↳ By the community?

– Yes

Notes: The worship was made at a mosque.

↳ By specific individuals?

– No

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention the principle of the places of worship.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

Notes: The text regulated activities of the bureaucracy

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– Yes

Notes: The text-coded regulations for the bureaucracy permanently

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– Yes

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– Yes

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– No

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned warfare under the principles of establishing religious freedom when a threat is directed against Islam.

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– Yes

Notes: The text set principles for the control of an institutionalized military body.

↳ Power to conscript?

– Yes

Notes: The text gave power to conscripts when the Islamic State faced attacks unexpectedly.

↳ Maintain a full-time military corps (E.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned the reward of a full-time guard of the Muslim society against

attack.

↳ Maintain a standing army?

– Yes

Notes: The text maintained a standing army for the defense of the religion of Islam.

↳ Particular types of training/readiness?

– I don't know

Notes: The text encouraged regular training on the military forces reserved to defend the religion of Islam.

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– Yes

Notes: The text restricted participation in any military organization that does not have a relationship to the defense of Islam.

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– I don't know

Notes: The text did not celebrate subjugation by exogenous military force.

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned Jizyah and Zakat as special taxes on certain people.

↳ Does the text require the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires religious groups to give out one-fifth of the booty to the government before distribution to the attendants of the Jihad.

↳ Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

Notes: No tax is levied on the group under none religious principles.

↳ Is taxation linked to an understanding of charitable giving?

– Yes

Notes: The tax is linked to charitable giving for the expectation of reward from Allah (SWT).

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

Notes: The text highlighted public interaction, especially Zakat and other recommendable characters.

↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?

– No

Notes: The text did not advocate for public food storage but rather; encouraged earning a livelihood and assisting the Poor through obligatory charity (Zakat) and non-obligatory charity (Sadaqat).

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?

– Yes

Notes: The text guided food distribution to the Poor under the principles of Obligatory Charity (Zakat).

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– Yes

Notes: The text analyzed some principles of public functions, especially truthfulness and sincerity.

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– Yes

Notes: The text regulated Islamic courts where justice is expected to be done for all.

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– Yes

Notes: The text regulated water management, which guided for judicious utilization of water to produce food that would be consumed and distributed on the prescribed principles of Zakat.

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– Yes

Notes: The text hinted at justice and truthfulness to regulate the transportation of the people.

↳ Other form of regulation of public works?

–Specify: Sanitation.

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned agricultural practices for food production.

↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– Yes

↳ Characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]

– Large-scale agriculture (E.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The text concerned any act that could support food production in the state.

↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– Yes

Notes: The text restricted only those foods prohibited by Islam.

↳ Characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: The text restricted the acceptance of food not lawfully accepted in Islam.

↳ Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Large-scale agriculture (E.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The text pointed to agriculture as means of gathering lawful food.

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: Most Islamic schools teach the text to students

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– Yes

Notes: The text institutionalized zakat as an institutionalized relief

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Notes: Zakat and Sadaqah are considered poverty relief

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text spelled the kind of students to benefit from its content

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Non-muslims

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– Yes

Notes: The text encouraged care for the elderly individuals

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Notes: It does not give any room for non-religious education

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Notes: Education is for all

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: Education is for both sexes

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Notes: The reward is in the heaven

Society & Institutions

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Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

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– Yes

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– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– Yes

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Does the text detail interaction with public works?

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Notes: The text highlighted public interaction, especially Zakat and other recommendable characters.

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Notes: The text guided food distribution to the Poor under the principles of Obligatory Charity (Zakat).

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– Yes

Notes: The text analyzed some principles of public functions, especially truthfulness and sincerity.

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– Yes

Notes: The text regulated Islamic courts where justice is expected to be done for all.

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– Yes

Notes: The text regulated water management, which guided for judicious utilization of water to produce food that would be consumed and distributed on the prescribed principles of Zakat.

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– Yes

Notes: The text hinted at justice and truthfulness to regulate the transportation of the people.

↳ Other form of regulation of public works?

– Specify: Sanitation.

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned Jizyah and Zakat as special taxes on certain people.

↳ Does the text require the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires religious groups to give out one-fifth of the booty to the government before distribution to the attendants of the Jihad.

↳ Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

Notes: No tax is levied on the group under none religious principles.

↳ Is taxation linked to an understanding of charitable giving?

– Yes

Notes: The tax is linked to charitable giving for the expectation of reward from Allah (SWT).

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned warfare under the principles of establishing religious freedom when a threat is directed against Islam.

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– Yes

Notes: The text set principles for the control of an institutionalized military body.

↳ Power to conscript?

– Yes

Notes: The text gave power to conscripts when the Islamic State faced attacks unexpectedly.

↳ Maintain a full-time military corps (E.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned the reward of a full-time guard of the Muslim society against attack.

↳ Maintain a standing army?

– Yes

Notes: The text maintained a standing army for the defense of the religion of Islam.

↳ Particular types of training/readiness?

– I don't know

Notes: The text encouraged regular training on the military forces reserved to defend the religion of Islam.

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– Yes

Notes: The text restricted participation in any military organization that does not have a relationship to the defense of Islam.

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– I don't know

Notes: The text did not celebrate subjugation by exogenous military force.

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned agricultural practices for food production.

↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– Yes

↳ Characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]

– Large-scale agriculture (E.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The text concerned any act that could support food production in the state.

↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– Yes

Notes: The text restricted only those foods prohibited by Islam.

↳ Characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: The text restricted the acceptance of food not lawfully accepted in Islam.

↳ Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Large-scale agriculture (E.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The text pointed to agriculture as means of gathering lawful food.

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